

(Dis)Trust of Slovenians in political institutions: The views of politicians

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Abstract

This article examines the issue of political trust in Slovenia, noting its considerable importance for the democracy-political system relationship. A range of empirical data show Slovenia is one of those countries where structurally low political trust is part of a long-running trend of decline, or at best it fluctuates in a way that reveals no trends. Qualitative data gathered in interviews with 14 politicians from different political institutions, show that Slovenia is similar to several other European countries, notably those in Central and Eastern Europe. It seems the performance perspective holds greater explanatory power than a critical citizen perspective. The findings of a cross-country survey and interviews conducted with politicians indicated many similarities among Slovenian citizens and politicians regarding these aspects, such as the importance of keeping one's campaign promises and being honest. The interviews also emphasize the importance of politicians being perceived to act professionally and the influence of the media, together with differences in trust across institutions and governance levels, with local-level accessibility proving to be especially relevant.

Keywords

political trust; Slovenia; representative institutions; politicians; performance

Introduction

While discussing representative democracy, one cannot overlook that it is in crisis today, and here the question of trust is also often raised. Trust is a complex, complicated, ambiguous, and multi-faceted concept that is one of the most studied areas in the social sciences, including conceptual, theoretical, operational as well as empirical aspects. Several scholars have indeed argued that when trust is being discussed one must distinguish a broad range of concepts and terms, which in practice are frequently used as synonyms of “trust”. One can also find trust being contrasted with counterparts like distrust, mistrust, skepticism, support, non-confidence, dissatisfaction, despite the implications of these concepts being quite different, as Lahusen (2024) notes.

In any case, the concept of political trust is generally used in political science. Political trust refers to the trust or support citizens place in political institutions, such as the parliament or government. Political trust constitutes a subjective evaluation of a relationship between a subject (the one who trusts) and an object (the one being trusted), yet the way they interact is also important (van der Meer and Hakhverdian, 2017). As van der Meer and Zmerli (2017: 4) state, political trust is fundamentally relational and situational; relational because it has a subject who trusts, and there is an object that is trusted; situational since it is commonly given or withheld depending on particular types of actions/environments. Even though several scholars have proven a link exists between social and political trust, building especially on cross-national research studies (see, e.g., Newton, 2009; Newton, Stolle and Zmerli, 2017), Uslaner (2017) warns there are noteworthy differences between political trust and social trust and the factors underlying them.

Although political trust is commonly viewed to be a valuable ingredient of representative democratic systems and the positive impacts it brings are largely celebrated, generally there are deep concerns with the signs that it is decreasing. However, scholars have more recently determined that identified blind or uncritical trust is just as problematic (Norris, 2023). A certain level of skepticism/mistrust in political institutions is namely an inherent part of modern representative democracies. As stated by van der Meer and van Erkel (2024) and Valgarðsson et al. (2025), multiple empirical research studies in past decades have revealed the structural erosion/decline in political trust. Still, other scholars disagree on whether any such erosion has occurred, and a further group of scholars argue that the fluctuations show no trends. Brunkert et al. (2023), Tufiş, Ghica, and Radu (2023), along with Lahusen (2024) and Valgarðsson et al. (2025), contend that even though notable differences in these trends or fluctuations have been established in various nations, the data nevertheless seem to show a general, albeit non-linear, global trend where trust is eroding or declining in political institutions, especially in political or representative institutions, parliaments, governments, and political parties.

The study of political trust has indeed clearly and overwhelmingly entailed a broad range of quantitative population survey methodologies where such trust was strongly linked to perceptions held by citizens/voters, although several studies also employed macro-level data and expert surveys coupled with macro-level objective data (e.g., levels of inflation, unemployment, and GDP growth).

Several empirical quantitative studies established that Slovenia forms part of these global trends of structurally low, declining or trendless fluctuations in political trust. After discussing the importance of political trust for democracy, in this article we focus on levels of political trust in Slovenia and how citizens view the issue of trustworthy politicians and the qualities they possess. Following quantitative analysis of a survey of European citizens (see Haerper et al., 2026), we apply a qualitative approach. Namely, our interest lies in how politicians (members of parliament, the executive, political party officials) on different levels (local, national, European) perceive political trust. The aim of the

article here is to present exploratory analysis that unveils their (differing) views, rhetorical stances, sentiments, and narratives concerning political trust and its importance. To that end, the second part of the article is based on analysis of 14 face-to-face interviews conducted in 2024 with politicians in Slovenia (see Belot et al, 2025). Both the survey of European citizens and the face-to-face interviews are part of the Horizon Europe project Trust in European Democracies (TRUEDEM) funded by the European Commission.

Political trust and democracy

As acknowledged by many scholars, political science is engaged in an ongoing debate on whether the erosion or decline in political trust indicates a crisis and if this is a special cause for concern. The discussion is hardly surprising when noting that Newton (2009) states the idea of trust being essential for social, economic, and political life is very old.

A range of ideas on why political trust is or can be important for democratic systems has indeed emerged. Valgarðsson et al. (2025) argue the debate on the great value of trust in political systems has its roots in both the normative concern that democratic systems should be based on the support/consent of their subjects and the more practical concern that regimes might not last long (or function well) if their members do not support them. Parallel to this is a belief that the trust of citizens in their national political institutions is needed for the legitimacy of a representative democracy. Still, it is not simply a question of legitimacy since many contend that political trust is important for the stability and quality of a democracy, even critical for its functioning and survival. Political trust is even seen as acting as a glue in the political system by holding elements of the system together and making sure it runs smoothly (Dodsworth and Cheeseman, 2020).

Political trust has been widely associated with several positive and desired outcomes, as well as viewed as a means for strengthening representative democracies, which logically leads to signs of low/dropping political trust becoming a substantial concern. Based on a review of multiple views and beliefs with respect to the value held by political trust for democracy, van der Meer and Zmerli (2017: 8), for instance, find that scholars have suggested that, on the macro level, low levels of trust would undermine a regime's stability, or, at best, signal structural challenges that call for the regime's institutions to be transformed, while on the meso level low political trust is linked to changes in the structures of party competition, chiefly by a providing fertile basis for new or populist parties to become successful at elections, and at the micro level, low political trust would induce support for democratic reform and erode citizens' compliance with the law.

Nonetheless, one can also find contradictory narratives on the importance of political trust, with too much political trust apparently also causing problems. For example, Warren (2017) states the trust-democracy relationship is complex because it is at the same time essential and a paradox. Democracies have namely arisen from distrust, particularly among elite power-holders (Warren, 2017). Haerpfer et al. (2022) as well as Devine and Valgarðsson (2024) note that, even though considerable literature engages in crisis talk to do with the falling political trust, almost no systematic evidence exists of its claimed relevance to democratic stability and the quality of government. Studies on various macro and micro levels reveal the causes or factors in political trust and the different links among them. In contrast, and as acknowledged by numerous scholars in recent years, systematic empirical research on the impact of political trust is notably scarce. This makes it reasonable to ask if indeed low and declining levels of political trust should be a concern in a representative democracy (van der Meer and Zmerli, 2017). In turn, serious doubts arise as to whether high levels of political trust are in fact "good" and low levels are "bad", as is constantly implied in the debates. It could well be the entire opposite

given that not every relationship of trust is supportive of democracy; trust might even be connected to support for authoritarian politics (Warren, 2017). The former approach emerged in the 1970s, arguing that democratic regimes' very survival is at stake when political trust is low, whereas although these days this notion is less explicit, allusions to the risk of a crisis in trust threatening the survival of representative democracies continue to appear in scholarly and public debates (van der Meer and Zmerli, 2017: 6).

Dawson and Krakoff (2024) establish that the literature is evidently divided on the relationship between political trust and democracy. Another body of literature (see Norris, 2011) suggests that while democracies fundamentally rely on the consent and support of those governed, a critically engaged citizenship able to hold the government accountable on key issues is a precondition for a democratic regime to be efficient and durable, and thus political trust can also hold both positive and negative implications for the development of a political system. Along this vein, scholars have more recently noted that falling levels of trust do not necessarily indicate a democracy is in crisis. Some even claim that distrust is a functional component of a democratic regime, with still more voices joining the chorus of those praising the value of skepticism in liberal democracies. Political scientists have begun to acknowledge that trust is not inevitably a democratic virtue, and distrust can help motivate civic participation and democratic governance (see Lahusen, 2024). Alternatively, as noted by van der Meer and van Erkel (2024), falling levels of political trust are not always problematic. Critical or assertive citizens exercising their democratic right to publicly criticize and challenge political institutions may thus have less trust in those institutions and these challenges are considered an important aspect of - not a threat to - the democratic political system and a sign that it is in good health (Dawson and Krakoff, 2024). Somewhere between these two literature streams lie two more modest suggestions; the first, that low levels of political trust do not cause but instead reflect a democratic malaise (van der Meer and Zmerli, 2017), the second that political trust and distrust are both essential for democracies - that is, while widespread distrust is viewed as detrimental for a given democratic state, a certain level of distrust can be healthy for it (Dawson and Krakoff, 2024).

While discussing political trust, there is another interesting debate that should not be overlooked. Among others, van der Meer and Zmerli (2017) argue that declining political trust might affect certain political institutions more than others: politicians and political parties more than parliaments, albeit, more than legal systems and regimes. Ouattara and van der Meer (2023) recently confirmed the findings of Zmerli and Newton on the hierarchical nature of political trust in each country. Similarly, Warren (2017) established that parts of political institutions are organized by function, professionally run, and protected from political agendas and patronage. These parts serve public purposes. In comparison, some institutions—parliaments, elected governments— are political and partial. For Warren (2017), it is normal that trust in less political institutions (police, judiciary, etc.) tends to be higher than trust in more political institutions—parliaments, even politicians. He adds that this has also been confirmed empirically frequently. Valgarðsson et al. (2025) also call to distinguish between political trust in various kinds of institutions. They refer to the distinction between representative or political institutions (chiefly parliaments, governments, political parties) on one hand, and non-representative implementing institutions (mostly the civil service, legal system, police) on the other, since trust in the former appears to capture one underlying dimension of trust, whereas trust in the police and courts captures a separate dimension, with trust in the civil services being somewhere in between. Given the variations of political trust in different kinds of political institutions, they contend the crisis of democracy thesis should focus on trust in representative institutions rather than non-representative ones because these are the core elements of a democratic government. This also

makes it impossible to talk about a crisis of trust in the state per se, only a crisis of trust in political and democratically mandated institutions (Valgarðsson et al., 2025: 20).

Quattara and van der Meer (2023) claim that, among others, their results suggest that low and falling political trust both lead to lower support for a representative democracy and bolster support for direct democratic policy- and decision-making. It is mostly “democratic innovations” that are mentioned in this respect. Indeed, Font and Blanco (2007: 558) argued the introduction of new forms of citizen participation was also justified by the need to create political trust, even though this was not the sole reason for developing them. Yet, despite several theorists and practitioners more recently suggesting that democratic innovations can impact political trust positively, evidence of this in the literature to date remains mixed (Gonthier, Ayme and Belot, 2024).

Slovenia – negative vibrations emanating from political institutions

In this section, we consider quantitative data on political trust where Slovenia is in the spotlight. The data were collected in a cross-national survey (24 European countries) carried out in 2025 (TRUEDEM) (see Haerpfer et al., 2026). Simultaneously, data from the longitudinal Slovenian Public Opinion Poll conducted by the Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre at the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, are also considered (see CJMMK, 2025).

TRUEDEM data for 2025 show that in Slovenia citizens have a very low level of trust in the national parliament, with just 3.1% of respondents answering they trust the parliament completely (only in Romania is this share lower). When adding those who stated they somewhat trust the parliament to the picture, the share rises to 20% (trust in the European Parliament is a little higher), yet still among the lowest. These shares are even lower when trust in political parties is considered— a paltry 2.4% of respondents trust them completely, while Romania, Greece, Spain, Czechia, and Croatia also recorded low trust levels (up to 4%), although in the last two countries the shares are considerably bigger when one adds those who somewhat trust parties.

Here there is an obvious discrepancy between a group of Central and Eastern European countries and a group of other European countries. The latter group expressed considerably higher levels of trust in parliaments and parties, noting that in a few countries (e.g., Spain, Greece, France) these levels were not high. Longitudinal data on the level of political trust in Slovenia confirm that these days it is low - only at the start of the democratic transition was the share of people who trusted the parliament and political parties notably higher, a share that has remained low despite some fluctuations (CJMMK, 2025).

Listhaug and Jakobsen (2017) attribute the described pattern in new European democracies to them having a shorter experience with democracy and weaker political institutions than countries with greater experience with a democratic system and a longer tradition of political institutions. Van der Meer (2017) believes the new democracies in Central and Eastern Europe experienced a “honeymoon effect” directly after the democratic transition, that saw a boost in political trust as a reflection of the high expectations which soon faded since the political institutions’ perceived performance features as a strong explanation of political trust in them. It is also obvious that the Great Recession and fiscal crisis which hit Slovenia after some delay in 2011, alongside the COVID-19 pandemic, and coupled with political institutions and leaders demonstrating that they were unable to deal with the crises or even attempting to take advantage of the COVID-19 crisis in the pursuit of certain authoritarian goals, had an important impact on the declining political trust (van der Meer and van Erkel, 2024) in Slovenia. Following the crises and fresh elections held in 2022, a few smaller improvements in political trust in Slovenia were observable, yet political trust has not been restored.

Figure 1. Trust in national parliaments and political parties (% who responded “trust completely”).

Data source: Haerpfer et al. (2026)

TRUEDEM data on the national parliament (the country’s most important political and representative body) show Slovenian citizens do not generally associate it with very positive vibrations or emotions (see Figure 2). Instead, on the whole it is not considered to be free of corruption, nor very competent and efficient, while at the same time serious concerns exist as to whether it always acts in the interest of all citizens, and if it is inclusive and representative of society.

A more refined evaluation of political authorities and their work is shown on the local level. The same applies when trust in government is under the microscope. It is low in Slovenia when the national government is being considered, yet higher in subnational governments (Haerpfer et al., 2026), a pattern that indeed may be expected given the data from other studies that Listhaug and Jakobsen (2017) presented.

The above-described idea of non-representative or implementing institutions enjoying higher levels of trust than representative political institutions is affirmed in Slovenia; trust in the armed forces, for instance, is much higher (over 40% of respondents trusted it completely or somewhat in 2025) than trust in representative institutions, civil society organizations are also among the more trusted institutions (with 45% of respondents completely or somewhat trusting them).

However, in a comparative perspective (see Haerpfer et al., 2026) these data show that Slovenians generally find it difficult to trust institutions. Slovenian Public Opinion Poll data (CJMMK, 2025) provide a similar picture, yet also here trust in the police can be added. The Police is a similarly or even more strongly trusted non-representative institution, irrespective of some sudden spikes and drops—especially the latter seem to be linked to specific leader being in or out of office (e.g., Prime Minister), or events (mass demonstrations and use of the police at such events) and scandals, because van der Meer and van Erkel (2024) established they may act as short-term explanations of bigger fluctuations in political trust.

Figure 2. Views on the parliament and regional/local authorities in Slovenia (mean values of agreement).

Data source: Haerpfer et al. (2026). Scales go from 1 (disagree completely) to 5 (agree completely).

Many scholars, including van der Meer and van Erkel (2024), have shown corruption is the most prominent set of structural explanations for low political trust. Irrespective of Corruption Perception Index data for Slovenia not being particularly bad (in 2024, Slovenia scored 60 on the 100-point scale), the Eurobarometer survey (EC, 2025) reveals worrying data. In 2025, the Eurobarometer showed that up to 85% of Slovenian respondents believe corruption is widespread in the country (EU average: 69%). The same percentage agrees corruption exists in the nation's public institutions. Most Slovenian respondents think that the giving and taking of bribes and abuse of power for personal gain is widespread, especially among politicians on different levels (59%), followed by political parties (57%). Still, in the last 12 months just 4% of respondents indicated they had experienced or witnessed any case of corruption. It seems that the Police is the most trusted institution when it comes to dealing with corruption. It seems obvious where the greatest problem with political trust in Slovenia lies. The TRUEDEM data also reveal that over 40% of respondents in Slovenia believe it is extremely or very likely that an MP would accept a bribe if offered one.

In Slovenia, a lot of citizens also do not believe in the accountability of politicians, despite it being precisely a key concept related to political trust or for the perception of a political institution as trustworthy (see van der Meer and Hakhverdian 2017; Haerpfer et al., 2022). TRUEDEM data for 2025 show that a mere 3.5% of respondents think it is extremely or very likely that were an official inquiry to find that government ministers had failed in their duties, they would be held accountable. The same survey shows that only a little more than 6% of respondents believe that if many people were to complain about a public service working badly, it would be improved. This is worth noting since scholars believe that many explanations of political trust are linked to an evaluation of the work or the perceived (also actual) performance of institutions (see van der Meer, 2017), or their ability to change/improve their performance.

Figure 3. Accountability of public services and government ministers (in %).

Data source: Haerpfer et al. (2026)

Figure 4. Qualities held by a trustworthy politician (% selecting a quality).

Data source: Haerpfer et al. (2026)

The perception of corruption and its importance for Slovenian citizens when considering politics and political trust is also echoed in responses to the question on the most crucial factors while assessing the trustworthiness of a politician (see Figure 4, respondents could select three from a list). Personal virtues are clearly the most critical of those listed factors. Fairness and honesty were mentioned by nearly half the respondents, followed by politicians' adherence to campaign promises (39.5%). Over the last two decades during campaigns in Slovenia the fight against (systemic) corruption was often combined with the appeal of “newness” - in the circumstances of new parties being quite successful at elections (Haughton, Krašovec and Cutts, 2024). Nevertheless, for example, the need for a politician to follow democratic values and norms was noted by 28.6% of respondents.

As noted while discussing the mechanisms/ways to bring about higher political trust, the literature mentions the introduction of new forms of citizen participation, especially democratic innovations. TRUEDEM survey data indicate that Slovenians are subject to “technocratic syndrome” since 45.7% of them believe experts should decide on a problem faced by the country if politicians, experts, and the public cannot agree on how to deal with it. However, 50.9% of them would also allow the people to hold this power. In fact, Slovenia has historically valued the tradition of including the people in policy- and decision-making that arises from its socialist past (e.g., the principle of self-management pursued in former socialist Yugoslavia), yet also the period before socialism (Zver, 1992; Lukšič, 2003). It is thus not surprising that Slovenians are among those to have introduced certain mechanisms to assure the people’s involvement in policy- and decision-making, notably referendums; many of referendums have been held. In comparison to other countries, although Slovenian citizens are not so enthused by other democratic innovations, at least 40% of them would like to participate in them (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Participation in ways of promoting democratic innovation in Slovenia (%).

Data source: Haerpfer et al. (2026)

A need for a politician who keeps promises (or does not promise too much) and is accessible to the public

In the last section of the article, we present results of analysis based on qualitative data gathered in face-to-face semi-structured interviews with politicians in Slovenia (see Belot et al., 2025). A total of 14 interviews was analyzed to meet the article's aims; 5 interviews with elected representatives of legislative bodies, 5 with representatives of executive bodies, and 4 with political party officials coming from different levels (local, national, European). The interviewees appearing in this article were anonymized by giving them role-based labels (legislative representatives, executive representatives, political party officials). The limited number of participants on specific levels of governance in a small-state context led us to omit governance level and gender to protect their anonymity.

All interviews were transcribed, anonymized, and translated into English using artificial intelligence tools like ChatGPT and DeepL. To provide the traceability and transparency of the research process, for this article the interview excerpts were edited only minimally for readability and clarity, with adjustments limited to word choice, while preserving the original meaning and context, and the spelling was adjusted to American English. The interviews generally examined a range of aspects of political trust and trustworthiness. Focus in the analysis was given to several issues we analyzed in greater detail: the importance of trust; reasons for distrust; the role of polarization; the role of the media; trust on the national and local levels; trust in various institutions; the role of politicians' personality; the characteristics of trustworthy politicians.

Importance of trust. Unsurprisingly, all interviewees generally saw political trust as a positive virtue and very important, while also agreeing that trust is volatile over time. The latter characteristic is often stressed, with a number of interviewees believing that political trust was higher when the democratic transition started than it has been in the last 20 years. This may partly be seen because of the above-mentioned "honeymoon effect" described by van der Meer (2017) having come to an end.

The leader of a political party (*political party official 3*) stated:

It decreases year by year. It seems to me that at the transition from socialism to democracy, expectations were extremely high, as shown by the participation in the plebiscite, in all the first elections, which means that people trusted both the newly established democratic institutions and the politics and politicians. Of course, perhaps since the quick changes that people expected, the rapid improvement in standards they desired, were not realized, trust in politics and political institutions greatly diminished.

A similar feeling was described by an interviewee from the local level:

Yet the fact is also that there is always less trust in politics. And I won't say, less this year than last, but I think that over the last decade, the last two decades, there has been very, very little trust. (*legislative representative 1*)

When the importance of political trust was being discussed by interviewees from different levels, "traditional" views that trust is a desirable thing were detected, such as:

I absolutely believe that all politicians should strive to gain the trust of citizens (*legislative representative 3*); It is one of the key things (*executive representative 5*); Yes, I think democratic politics is based on trust (*executive representative 3*); Yes, I think that the trust of citizens in the political system and in the system in a broader context is crucial for any segment of public life and any element of policy formation and implementation (*executive representative 4*); It gives you greater confidence on a personal, emotional level in what you are doing. /.../ So, trust is mainly very useful for the legitimacy of decisions that you make yourself (*legislative representative 4*).

Political party official 3 elaborated on the importance of trust from personal and institutional points of view:

For my personal work as a politician, public trust is vital. It's a fundamental basis. Without the trust of the citizens, I wouldn't even have been elected as an MP. Without the trust of the citizens, I could not operate in this political circus or these political stories. As for the institution, the greater the trust citizens have in an institution, the greater power it has in managing social relations in the country. And it also more easily implements and carries out certain things. So, trust is key, with the difference that institutions in some democratic countries remain somewhat constant unless the constitution otherwise shapes or changes them, regardless of greater or lesser trust. Meanwhile, politicians who operate within these institutions change depending on trust. When trust fades, or is no longer there, that politician is no longer part of those institutions.

A mayor held similar views:

Personally, as a politician, you want the residents, the citizens, to trust you in the matters that at the end of the day you handle on their behalf. The institution itself is then significantly more successful in its implementation of all guidelines outlined if it has the trust of the public. At the end of the day, this is probably also shown in the effectiveness of policy implementation because when residents have high trust or trust, the barriers, opposition, and so on are considerably less than otherwise if that trust was not present. (*executive representative 2*)

According to this mayor, trust is especially valuable when decisions involving less popular financial outcomes must be made. Another mayor went further and expanded on importance of trust, stating:

Don't play around with trust, absolutely don't. Nowhere, in any area. Not in the family, not among friends. Because trust is really a commitment and a bond. And it is right that you do not disappoint. You disappoint this way; intentionally or unintentionally. /.../ And it's easier to work, because you have support when you start a project, you say I have support, they trusted me, now it's on me. Trust is not something to play with. It is very, very important. Even in the long run. (*legislative representative 1*)

The mayor added that he believes that, once it is lost, trust cannot be restored.

Keeping one's promises is the key. Interviewees in Slovenia gave several reasons for the low or falling political trust, which are similar to those listed by different scholars. The inability of politicians to keep the promises they have made, typically in electoral campaigns, was most often mentioned here. Several statements (shorter or longer) made by interviewees indicate the particular importance of the issue of political performance.

I think politics has a lot of responsibility here, then what they promise, they really should do. (*executive representative 5*)

The main reasons are just that: we like to eat our words. We promise something, then we do not stand by it. Again, there are hundred reasons why we eat our words. Sometimes you just throw a bone out during elections, well, they will grab it, and it doesn't matter what happens tomorrow. Sometimes, as I mentioned before, we dive into promises too quickly before even checking if it's feasible, where the problems lie, what are the problems. (*legislative representative 1*)

In some ways, probably yes, because we have politicians who make empty promises that they are not even given to be fulfilled. I think there is another set of politicians who promise too quickly and then see that the matter is more complex and that everything does not go so fast, and then citizens again feel that we have somehow deceived them and that we actually do not want to solve the problem (*legislative representative 3*)

How should I say this /.../ in Slovenian, it would be "they do not meet the expectations and do not deliver on what they promised." This leads to significant disappointment. People have expectations, some hope, and when this hope and expectation are not met, what always comes

next is disappointment. So, it is crucial for trust that what you promise, you also deliver. /.../ And anyone who comes up—appears like a Miss World, “we will strive for peace in the world and for everyone to be nice and fine”, everyone places their expectations in this box, then they are not met, and we always have new major disappointments. (*political party official 3*)

Then there are also decisions, the way of working, but primarily, in my judgment, it is the determination of the execution of what a given politician has announced or promised, whether in the campaign or in the course of performing their function. /.../ Trust is built when people see the effect, when they see the result, actually what was announced, what was initiated, initiated in the context of keeping promises. (*executive representative 2*)

Scandals and crises are important. As shown above, the most prominent set of structural explanations for low political trust include corruption and different affairs; this is also revealed in the statements of Slovenian politicians. While it seems that scandals are important in themselves, we must not forget the question of how they are resolved; an aspect mentioned by a politician:

Perhaps, I would add that there are often some scandals, or something is discovered, and then there is no epilogue, or something is artificially induced and perpetuated endlessly, and yet in reality, it is not an important matter, or actually involves serious offenses, and people do not see that it was punished, changed, that someone was held accountable. That's why they also lose trust in institutions, because the problem was not adequately remedied, or appropriate sanctions were not applied. (*legislative representative 5*)

Crises were also viewed as a potential turning point in low or declining trust.

I think that in Slovenia, the break in trust in institutions actually came around the same time as the financial crisis. And then with the emergence and intensification of rhetoric at the time. /.../ And then also with the migration crisis. (*legislative representative 4*)

Indeed, crises here were not seen as problems in themselves but in relation to how they caused changes in rhetoric. Still, crises can also provide opportunities to boost political trust, as two politicians described:

For example, the government had trust when there were floods, when the prime minister appeared after the floods and clearly stated what should be done, how they would do it, then trust rose a lot. (*legislative representative 2*)

If you look, for example, at the terrible floods that happened, if you ask me, those floods helped this government. That it could do something in this crisis. (*executive representative 5*)

Polarization matters. In the literature, polarization is also mentioned while discussing political trust, making it hardly surprising that the issue was raised by Slovenian interviewees. Here, we note a local politician's (*executive representative 1*) assessment:

And maybe also mutual recrimination, which is part of the democratic debate, where politicians engage on very different communication levels and thus, of course, “dig holes” for each other. Absolutely at work, they greatly affect trust, especially among opposing voters, who are also part of it, especially if it's the government.

Legislative representative 4 talked along similar lines:

I see that then, in the polarized society we are living in, trust in institutions really depends on that part of the electorate that is in power. So now, when we are probably in power, one part of the people trust the institutions, and when someone else is in power, another part of the people trust the institutions.

A local politician (*legislative representative 1*) further illustrated the issue

It's hard to convince a convinced person, and as I mentioned earlier, citizens also like to define themselves, like in a football match with the white and yellow, or even green, red... it doesn't matter, for one side or the other, they define themselves and it's hard to convince them to no longer root for [Club A] but for [Club B].

Another local politician (*executive representative 2*) declared:

If a politician advocates different values, different principles than a citizen, it's a fact that there will be no trust in this relationship between that politician and the citizen. First, trust must be built on a value scale that should be as similar as possible, aligned. That's the first point where trust can already fall, or you enter the interaction completely without trust if these values are diametrically opposed.

Who is occupying the positions? Interestingly, Slovenian politicians hold critical views on the structure of various political institutions since they see the question of personnel or the political elite as a key determinant of political trust. The representative of a political party made a point based on a more general aspect of parties in Slovenia, that consequently is leading to a problem with personnel as well.

Generally, the parties have low political trust due to a sort of folklore in Slovenia where some people don't want parties, and instead movements, platforms, forums, lists. /.../ However, it seems to me that great harm is being done to the democracy because there is an attempt to attach all negative things to political parties. This of course breaks down political parties institutionally and degrades the quality of the personnel since a political party that has a tradition, of course, has some staffing procedures. Above all, the team within this party knows each other very well and can contribute to a staffing process, an educational process, always contributing to higher quality politics and the institutions in which these politicians operate. (*political party official 3*)

Another interviewee made bigger claims:

/.../ is my opinion, the biggest problem with Slovenian politics is that we don't have people who know how to manage and lead state systems. /.../ In the last 20 years, we have not had the systematic integration of cadre production. /.../ it is at the same time a problem, it is also in my opinion an outcome especially of this fundamental distrust in political parties in Slovenia. /.../ As for trust in the parliament, in my estimation it is empirically provable why the trend with trust over the years has probably lowered. If we just look at the most systematic view of education levels, or levels of general knowledge in the Slovenian parliament, I think that in the last 20 years this level has dropped significantly. (*legislative representative 4*)

Another interviewee was concerned with the (lack of) professionalization of politics:

Politics as a profession/.../ I can't imagine that anyone could just go into healthcare to do something or, in the end, to be a mechanic, let's say. Here, anyone can do whatever they want. Everyone thinks they are called upon to do it. And qualified, without in any way first having had primary political socialization and I think here is where our key system is not of the individual but of the political space.

The interviewee added:

Simply because they don't have a base behind them because they lack the political socialization of candidates to bring them as political animals to the point where they can perform the function as needed. But they are new, I won't say dilettantes, but even in the theatre we can find "naturals" who are relatively good, but most cannot gather ten people on the street and tell them, now you will go to the Drama theatre to play Hamlet. Because it won't work. Here it seems that it does. (*executive representative 4*)

A local politician (*executive representative 1*) offered a comparison in this respect:

Today, politics buys trust mainly with excursions from other professions. Now we are looking at the European elections, the Freedom Movement is including a doctor because it is apparently a more trustworthy profession than if "politics" were to appear at the top of its list. This somehow extinguishes the situation of actual trust in some structures of politics.

Another politician mentioned the problem with successful new parties or faces in Slovenia in past decades:

In short, to completely trust these new faces and then to be disappointed with them is, on one hand, justified, because none have lived up to those expectations, and on the other hand, it is also not at all justified because what else can you expect from someone who is doing this for the first time. (*political party official 4*)

A somewhat different point in terms of the importance of personnel was made by another politician who saw a link between trust in political institutions and who leads them:

Unfortunately, I notice that trust is very connected to leadership. It depends on who is at the helm. Whether that person is trustworthy or not. (*executive representative 5*)

Is the media to be blamed? The influence of the media on the level of political trust was also often highlighted. Interviewees mainly referred to the negative influence of the media on trust, including as part of the prevalent logic of the media system in a global perspective yet also as a demand/expectation arising from society; for example:

And of course, unfortunately, the market in Slovenia is small and the media adapts to the people. They want scandals, populist headlines. Unfortunately, I also think that politicians adapt to this mode of communication, which is appealing. (*legislative representative 3*)

And in fact, in the media space, it seems to me that this part of negative elements is extremely exposed, while the positive part is very rarely. Simply due to the characteristics of the media space. This doesn't only happen here, and from that perspective it's certainly one of the things that has a negative impact. (*executive representative 4*)

I mean, if the average person dedicates a few minutes a day to politics, they would like to have some positive stories, but the vast majority are negative stories, from scandals onwards. (*political party official 2*)

Another interviewee was more critical:

Trust is important, but there are quite a few problems. This means, we now have, how should I put it, media trying to undermine trust in politicians. That means, they try to undermine the integrity of politicians. (*political party official 1*)

The importance of media reports and persistence of the image of politics or a politician they create is illustrated by the explanation given by a politician:

Then also conversations with people and explanations for this. Because it often happens that manipulations occur, either through the media or on social networks. /.../ And I have often had to correct the damage caused by certain media on the ground by talking to people. And this is a much more extensive, harder job, and you can never reach everyone. (*legislative representative 5*)

A more neutral statement was provided by a mayor who had evidently linked media reports with political trust, and also noted that in this respect the media are more important concerning the building of (dis)trust on the national level:

So, the media definitely has such an important role, especially when the institution is more distant from the residents, so they cannot also directly follow it and actually understand the effects themselves. (*executive representative 2*)

Indeed, only one politician offered a different view on the role of the media:

To say now that if the media had reported more nicely, but the task of the media in a democracy is to be critical of power, to expose irregularities ... /.../ If the media has an influence, not because the media decides to report in a certain way, but if the media influences distrust in politics it is because they are doing their job. (*political party official 4*)

Local vs. national level. In the first part of the article, we stated that political trust is usually higher on the local level than the national one. Several interviewees agreed with this view, while local

politicians in Slovenia also conceded that, for various reasons, it is easier for them to assure and retain political trust.

On the local level, it is definitely different because you have direct contact with people, or they have direct contact with the mayor. Everything else on the state level, and on the world level, is only seen on TV, it's hard to comment. On the local level, they tug on your sleeve in the grocery store, at the gas station, they tell you their opinion, their viewpoint. /.../ So, here there is a little more trust since they also know you on a personal level. /.../ But there is definitely greater trust on a local level than on the national one because they feel they have some influence, or that have some impact on events. (*legislative representative 1*)

In a similar manner, a mayor noted the importance of vicinity:

Somehow, as the institutions are more distant from individuals, this level of trust decreases, which is logical. More specifically, those institutions that are of course closest to the people usually, follow them the most, see their activities the most, and thus, there is somewhat greater trust there. Whereas the more we move away, namely, towards the state level or even further to the European level, I assess that this level of trust is ever lower. (*executive representative 2*)

In firefighters and civil protection forces we trust! Several studies have shown that the degree of trust is linked to the nature of a given institution. In Slovenia, it is also evident that some institutions are more trusted than others, while in the interviews explanations similar to those found abroad were offered concerning the hierarchical nature of political trust. Firefighters and civil protection forces, yet also the army and the police were frequently mentioned as highly trusted institutions. Still, in the case of the latter, several interviewees cautioned that the police is a good example of how quickly trust can be lost when the political realm tries to interfere in its work.

For example, civil protection, firefighters have a high level of trust. Meanwhile, political institutions less so because of repeated disappointments. (*legislative representative 5*)

The most trustworthy institutions, firefighters, the police, and similar ones, about which I actually don't know, civil defense, everyone involved from this context—these are services or institutions to which people always turn and always get an immediate response and are ultimately established for that reason. (*executive representative 2*)

Political institutions whose work is associated with naturally inherent conflict are importantly less trusted, especially in Slovenia which has a tradition of consensual politics. One politician (*political party official 4*) put it this way:

I think in Slovenia it's very much the case that people dislike conflict. Generally, trust is lower in those institutions where there is political conflict: the National Assembly, the government, or those where there are specific reasons or corruption scandals, when things come to light. People truly prefer consensual politics and where they see that, they also give trust, which is also somewhat problematic from the political process perspective. Because the political process cannot proceed without conflict, and it seems to me that this is a somewhat problematic expectation held by citizens. /.../ It seems to me that this aspect of the Slovenian political culture is also problematic. I think that people find it hard to understand politics, they very much approach it with a dismissive view of conflict, that conflict is necessarily something bad, it seems to me, that is, that this is somewhat widespread in Slovenian political culture.

Another interviewee had similar view:

I feel that the parliament has the lowest trust, perhaps because of the intensity of the debates, perhaps also because during this time we have not been able to properly educate the wider community that varying opinions in parliament do not mean quarrelling and arguing, but just the confrontation of some opinions, which is a normal process in forming some democratic decisions. /.../ If you have someone as the president of the parliament, president of the republic whom the broader public trusts a lot, that trust can be high, and it can be the same with the government,

or the opposite, if that trust is not there. /.../ I would say that the personal aspect or trust in some politicians is also then reflected in trust in the institution. (*political party official 3*)

A local politician (*executive representative 1*) observed important differences between the local and national levels:

While on the state level it works much more abstractly, these are political ideas, of course, there are sympathies and antipathies, the media is full of these people. /.../ But it is established quite differently more on this ideological basis, while on the local level it is really very personalized and strongly tied to the person, personality, which I think then also soon begins to reflect on the functioning of the politician as the bearer of them.

Another politician noted differences among political institutions on the national level: But still, I think that institutions which deal less directly with day-to-day issues, where either some flaws or undesirable operations by the state are also visible, are undesirable in the sense that I am not the most happy if an institution does not issue a building permit, then I would probably say that there is definitely something wrong there. And at the same time, if it is an institution of the president of the state or which generally is seen as holding a ceremonial function, where you say, wow, and if I can even identify with that person, who is there an ad personam on the function, there is definitely more trust. (*executive representative 4*)

Ingredients for a trustworthy politician in Slovenia. One question enquired directly about the characteristics a trustworthy politician in Slovenia should possess. Here one politician (*legislative representative 5*) saw a discrepancy among the wishes expressed and the reality in the support gained by parties at elections:

Definitely, as holders of political functions and as decision-makers, we should locate these norms in the highest places and act based on them. Unfortunately, it is not always so and I will say again, in elections, when people say they want honest politicians, then they vote for someone who is anything but that, then one wonders what people actually want and why we complain about the kind of MPs we have, the kind of government we have, what kind of decision-makers, whether they have received such support. So here I see a big discrepancy between what we say are the greatest values that politicians should consider and act upon, and on the other hand, which values receive the most support, that there is a big gap.

The outlined reasons for the low trust in political institutions together with the quantitative data from the TRUEDEM survey mean it is no surprise that also politicians viewed the keeping of promises made as among the most important ingredients of a trustworthy politician, for instance:

To try not to promise things that are not realistic, or touch on topics you are not familiar with because it most often happens that you promise something that is completely unrealistic, but maybe you didn't know that was the case. (*political party official 2*)

One interviewee linked this idea to integrity when stating:

/.../ connected with what I last spoke about, integrity, one of those, I would say, which, citizens value, generally keeping promises, or directions that are announced, therefore achieving results, that is, efficiency in this context, and at the end of the day, it is definitely also to ascertain that, I would say, the level of humanity among, that is, the ability to somehow identify with the majority of citizens, is definitely something that they recognize as that, as positive. (*executive representative 2*)

Noting that coalition governments are the norm in Slovenia, a warning issued by a politician about this aspect was probably warranted:

We know that all political decisions are made by consensus with multiple political options and call for dialogue—a bit of giving and taking. However, you must not deviate significantly from your direction. This means you should not support things you had previously assured voters you were firmly against. (*political party official 1*)

To the virtues of a trustworthy politician, we can add efficiency along with the openness or accessibility of a politician. One interviewee warned that sometimes these concepts are hard to evaluate:

But now we have a serious problem, how will we measure what that is. What is transparency? What is efficiency? What is acting for the general public interest? /.../ So, in principle, yes. Yes, those are definite traits that a politician should have, but now, whether a politician has them or not depends greatly on which glasses you are using to look at him. (*executive representative 4*)

Another interviewee made several interesting points about the relationship between two virtues in Slovenia:

If people feel that a politician is honest, they might also tolerate him being less efficient. Or if people hold the impression that a politician is extremely efficient, they will also tolerate him if he is slightly less than honest. (*political party official 3*).

Openness or accessibility was also mentioned by numerous interviewees. *Legislative representative 2* stated:

/.../ it's important to go out into the field... /.../ Sometimes you're like a psychotherapist, but sometimes you can't solve, but it's enough, that you listened to them. And this certainly strengthens trust.

Probably, the most, the most important is direct contact. (*legislative representative 2*)

According to the TRUEDEM survey, the need for a politician to comply with democratic values and norms did not feature among the most important qualities in a trustworthy politician in Slovenia. As *executive representative 2* noted while asked about the importance of democratic values and norms for political trust:

Yes, I think, definitely, yes, I will say they are, but, but I don't see them as the key ones, I don't see them as the key ones. At the end of the day, we have a situation in Slovenia where we can see, I don't know, concerning the rule of law, that some politicians have a very high level of trust among citizens, but at the same time, we cannot classify them among those who actually support the story, so they are important, but not key.

This view was shared by another interviewee:

No, I think that is less important, which is a pity. (*political party official 3*)

Among other characteristics of a trustworthy politician, interviewees mentioned principledness, tolerance, truthfulness, and integrity. However, one interviewee claimed:

These are comments I hear, but it is not said that these qualities attract the greatest support at elections. Because elections are often won by populism, and other things. (*legislative representative 5*)

This discrepancy or a certain level of skepticism is also reflected in a statement by *political party official 2* when the transparency of a politician's whole life is mentioned:

Someone who is /.../ very often before the courts, I don't believe they would receive the same trust as someone who just normally goes through life, completes all their tasks. So, I think transparency and honesty. We still look for honesty in people, but at the same time we believe that those who somehow manage to bypass the system are really something special.

Executive representative 3 distinguished two broad understandings of political trustworthiness:

Let's say, there are two types of politicians. Of course, with nuances. People appreciate in a pragmatic politician the ability to set goals and achieve them. That is, using narrative logic. We say, we will build 5,000 [units] and then we show we are capable of doing that. Then you have, let's say, the ideological type of politician who holds a Manichean view of the world, which is black-and-white; us here—they there. Here they primarily value consistency; to see that this politician persists in the light and fights against the darkness.

Conclusion

The concept of political trust is very important in political science because it holds several implications. As we have shown, discussions on the importance and causes of political trust are quite common, also due to the considerable empirical evidence that generally indicates a decline or fluctuation in political trust. However, discussions about the importance of political (dis)trust have grown more diverse in recent decades.

As described, in a comparative perspective Slovenia belongs to the group of countries that has faced relatively structurally low trust, yet recently also declining or at best trendless fluctuations in political trust for various reasons, which in any case are similar to those observed in many other countries. Moreover, similar patterns and reasons can be seen while dealing with political trust, as affirmed by the recent cross-country public opinion poll data we presented in the article.

These quantitative data led us to also address the issue of political trust with qualitative data. Based on the perceptions held by politicians (members of parliament, executive and political party officials) from different levels (local, national, European) gathered in interviews about political trust, our exploratory analysis revealed (varying) views, rhetorical stances, sentiments, and narratives to do with political trust, its importance, perceived reasons for the current situation along with potential measures or steps that could be taken (by politicians) to improve it. All 14 interviewees namely agreed that political trust is important for democracy and a political system for different, yet still traditionally the most exposed reasons. In this respect, politicians in Slovenia do not view the low political trust as beneficial or a factor motivating civic participation (critical citizen perspective) and regard the low or declining political trust as problematic.

It seems that when it comes to political trust the performance perspective is the closest to Slovenian politicians. Its significance is namely linked to the expectations citizens hold of politicians, especially the question of the (in)ability to keep the promises made (mostly during the election campaign). Performance or efficacy appears to be more important than the issue of corruption, or as some politicians described, people in Slovenia will in practice also tolerate a politician with a lower integrity if they are efficient. Slovenians are clearly looking for honesty and integrity, yet simultaneously they believe that someone who manages to bypass the system is exceptional.

Despite the fiscal, economic, and COVID-19 crises representing turning point in the trend of political trust also in Slovenia, as shown by various survey data, it seems that crises can also represent a window of opportunity for politicians. The idea that the level of political trust varies subject to the kind of institution being discussed is also close to politicians in Slovenia. It is clear that several non-representative or non-political institutions enjoy greater trust than political ones, especially those where conflicts are a normal part of their functioning. It seems this is not surprising for the interviewees, particularly when Slovenians' traditional disapproval of conflicts or their calls to assure consensual politics are considered. The differences in political trust in institutions on various levels is also not a surprise, notably when the outlined importance of the openness or accessibility of politicians is taken into account - on the local level, it is much easier to provide it.

It is noteworthy that many interviewees linked the decline in political trust to issue of personnel, largely the question of the quality and/or lack of professionalism of politicians. Several interviewees also placed this problem in the context of the electoral success of new parties over the last decade or two. The media was also viewed as an important determinant of political trust.

While we are aware that more in-depth analysis must be conducted to be able to form any more solid conclusions, we can say that citizens and politicians in Slovenia appear to share many views on political trust, its determinants, and importance. Nonetheless, as a few interviewees warned, there

is also a gap between citizens' ideas about what causes political trust and the characteristics of trustworthy politicians on one side, and electoral support given to politicians who possess or lack these virtues on the other.

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References

- Belot, Céline et al. 2025. *Trust in European Democracies: Politicians, Civil Society, and Citizens across 10 European Countries* [data set]. TRUEDEM Consortium, with the participation of the Chair Jean Monnet Montréal.
- Brunkert, Lennart, Puranen, Bi, Turska-Kawa, Agnieszka, and Christian Welzel. 2023. "Institutional Trust in Europe: Dimensions, Levels, and Dynamics from a Latent Class Perspective." *Working Paper no. 4.2, TRUEDEM: Trust in European Democracies Project*.
[https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D4.2. Institutional Trust In Europe Dimensions%20C Levels and Dynamics.pdf](https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D4.2.Institutional%20Trust%20In%20Europe%20Dimensions%20C%20Levels%20and%20Dynamics.pdf).
- Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja (CJMMK). 2025. "E-gradiva." Accessed March 30, 2025.
<https://www.cjm.si/gradiva/>.
- Dawson, Andrew, and Isabel L. Krakoff. 2024. "Political trust and democracy: The critical citizens thesis re-examined." *Democratization*, 31(1): 90–112.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13510347.2023.2257607>.
- Devine, Daniel, and Viktor Orri Valgarðsson. 2024. "Stability and change in political trust: Evidence and implications from six panel studies." *European Journal of Political Research*, 63(2): 478–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12606>.
- Dodsworth, Susan, and Nic Cheeseman. 2020. *Political trust: The glue that keeps democracies together*. London: Westminster Foundation for Democracy. Accessed December 12, 2025.
https://www.wfd.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/WFD_May2020_Dodsworth_Cheeseman_PoliticalTrust.pdf.
- European Commission (EC). 2025. "Citizens' attitudes towards corruption in the EU in 2025." *Eurobarometer*. Accessed November 11, 2025.
<https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3361>.
- Font, Joan, and Ismael Blanco. 2007. "Procedural legitimacy and political trust: The case of citizen juries in Spain." *European Journal of Political Research*, 46(4): 557–89.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.2007.00701.x>.
- Gonthier, Frédéric, Aymé, Prunelle, and Céline Belot. 2024. "Political Trust and Democratic Innovations: State-of-the-Art Report." *Working Paper no. 9.1. TRUEDEM: Trust in European Democracies Project*.
[https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D9.1 Report on political trust and democratic innovations.pdf](https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D9.1_Report_on_political_trust_and_democratic_innovations.pdf).

- Haerpfer, Christian et al. 2022. *World Values Survey: Round Seven – Country-Pooled Datafile Version 6.0*. Madrid, Spain and Vienna, Austria: JD Systems Institute and WWSA Secretariat. Accessed 15 December 2025. <https://doi.org/10.14281/18241.24>.
- Haerpfer, Christian et al. 2026. *Trust in European Democracies*. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/FUOJUE>, Harvard Dataverse.
- Haughton, Tim, Krašovec, Alenka, and David Cutts. 2024. “Jumping on the new party bandwagon: The 2022 elections and the development of party politics in Slovenia.” *Europe-Asia Studies*, 76(10): 1526–1550. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09668136.2024.2378832>.
- Lahusen, Christian. 2024. “Trust and distrust in political institutions: Conceptual and theoretical reassessments”. *Journal of Political Sociology* 2(1): 80-109. <https://doi.org/10.54195/jps.19659>.
- Listhaug, Ola, and Tor Georg Jakobsen. 2017. “Foundations of political trust.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Social and Political Trust*, edited by Eric M. Uslaner, 559–578. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190274801.013.14>.
- Lukšič, Igor. 2003. “Corporatism packaged in pluralist ideology: The case of Slovenia.” *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 36(4): 509–525. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48609481>.
- Newton, Kenneth, Stolle, Dietlind, and Sonja Zmerli. 2017. “Social and political trust.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Social and Political Trust*, edited by Eric M. Uslaner, 37–56. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190274801.013.20>.
- Newton, Kenneth. 2009. “Social and political trust.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Political Behavior*, edited by Russell J. Dalton and Hans-Dieter Klingemann, 342–361. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199270125.003.0018>.
- Norris, Pippa. 2011. *Democratic Deficit: Critical Citizens Revisited*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Norris, Pippa. 2023. “Literature Review and Research Paper on Measuring Trust.” *Working Paper no. 1.1. TRUEDEM: Trust in European Democracies Project*. [https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D1.1.Literature review and research paper on measuring trust.pdf](https://www.truedemdata.eu/truedem/D1.1.Literature%20review%20and%20research%20paper%20on%20measuring%20trust.pdf).
- Ouattara, Ebe, and Tom van der Meer. 2023. “Distrusting democrats: A panel study into the effects of structurally low and declining political trust on citizens’ support for democratic reform.” *European Journal of Political Research*, 62(4): 1101–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12561>.
- Tufiş, Claudiu, Ghica, Luciana, and Bogdan Radu. 2023. “Long-Term Trends of Political Trust Dynamics (1980–2023): Dataset and Codebook.” *Working Paper no. 1.3, TRUEDEM: Trust in European Democracies Project*. <https://www.truedem.eu/resources-and-deliverables/secondary-data-analysis/political-trust-database>.
- Uslaner, Eric M. 2017. “The study of trust.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Social and Political Trust*, edited by Eric M. Uslaner, 3–14. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190274801.013.39>

- Valgarðsson, Viktor et al. 2025. "A crisis of political trust? Global trends in institutional trust from 1958 to 2019." *British Journal of Political Science*, 55: e15. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007123424000498>.
- van der Meer, Tom W. G. 2017. "Democratic input, macroeconomic output and political trust." In *Handbook on Political Trust*, edited by Sonja Zmerli and Tom W. G. van der Meer, 270–284. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- van der Meer, Tom W. G., and Armen Hakhverdian. 2017. "Political trust as the evaluation of process and performance: A cross-national study of forty-two European democracies." *Political Studies*, 65(1): 81–102. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032321715607514>.
- van der Meer, Tom W. G., and Patrick F. A. van Erkel. 2024. "Moving beyond the political trust crisis debate: Residual analyses to understand trends in political trust." *European Journal of Political Research*, 63(3): 1240-1257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12645>
- van der Meer, Tom W. G., and Sonja Zmerli. 2017. "The deeply rooted concern with political trust." In *Handbook on Political Trust*, edited by Sonja Zmerli and Tom W. G. van der Meer, 1–15. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Warren, Mark. 2017. "Trust and democracy." In *The Oxford Handbook of Social and Political Trust*, edited by Eric M. Uslaner, 75–94. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190274801.013.5>
- Zver, Milan. 1992. "Korporativizem v slovenski politični misli v 20. in 30. letih." *Časopis za kritiko znanosti* 20 (148/149): 37–45.

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